

Turkish Librarianship: A Selected Bibliography

Yaşar Tonta*

The main purpose of this bibliography is to list some of the journal articles, reports and books on Turkish libraries, information centers and archives which appeared in the international professional literature. It is prepared primarily for those attending the 61st IFLA Council and General Conference in Istanbul with the hope that the bibliography can be used as a reference point by the library and information professionals and researchers wishing to further their knowledge about Turkish library and information scene. Such a bibliography has to be selective by its very nature. I tried to include both historical and current items in the bibliography to provide a fairly comprehensive coverage. Most items were written in Western languages.

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* Associate Professor Yaşar Tonta is with the Department of Library Science, Hacettepe University, 06532 Beytepe, Ankara.

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